

MODEL OF COMMUNITY EMPOWERMENT OF SELF-RELIANT ACTIVE STANDBY VILLAGE IN ACCOMODATING THE REDUCING PREVALENCY OF STUNTING IN GARUT REGENCY

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Abstract

This study aims to build a model for empowering rural communities to be active and independent within the framework of reducing the prevalence of stunting in Garut Regency, West Java Province. This research uses a combination method (Mixed-Methods) with a concurrent embedded strategy; in this study, the combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches is used together to support the research to be studied. This study uses a Soft System Methodology (SSM) approach. The SSM method is also action research that aims to solve complex problematic situations. To meet the objectives of this study, the SSM analysis consists of (1) CATWOE analysis, (2) Role analysis and (3) Social Systems Analysis. The results of this study are in the form of a model for empowering community to be active and self-reliant, which is the result of the integration of conceptual thinking and the consequences of reality that complement each other in producing the model. This model is a solution to overcome problems in achieving self-reliance, active standby village (in Garut Regency, West Java Province). The recommendation that can be given is that the local government, especially Garut Regency, can run the model as an effort to overcome the problems that have occurred so far in achieving self-reliance of an active standby village.

Keywords: Community Empowerment, Model, Self-Reliant, Active Standby Village.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of empowerment is the granting of authority and trust to local communities to determine various forms of development activity programs and their needs through efforts to protect, strengthen, develop, consult and advocate to improve their level of social welfare (Ikeda et al., 2013; Bloem et al., 2013; Hanafy & Hegab, 2019). Empowerment is the granting of authority, a delegation of authority or granting autonomy to lower ranks. The essence of empowerment is an effort to generate all existing capabilities to achieve goals. Achievement goals through the growth of motivation, initiative, creativity, and rewards and recognition for those who excel (Purnomo et al., 2020; Angelia et al., 2020).

Community empowerment that is carried out in the health sector in supporting aspects of human development is the implementation of self-reliant, active-standby villages that focus on handling health. People with health conditions can carry out various activities and contribute to development. Health is the dream of all humans because a healthy body can carry out activities without physical limitations. Health is one of the basic human needs (Okereke, 2021; Fenn et al., 2012; Hossain et al., 2017). The definition of health is a prosperous condition of body, soul, and society that allows everyone to be economically productive; therefore, health is the basis for recognizing the degree of humanity.

Efforts to reduce stunting are not only through the government's role but also need all parties' contributions. In line with the goals set out in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) or the Sustainable Development Goals Agenda as a global development agreement, there are several targets related to human development. One of these is the third goal, ensuring healthy lives and improving the well-being of people of all ages. In target 3.1, there is a commitment that by 2030, the maternal mortality rate will decrease to less than 70 per 100,000 live births. This target aims to end child mortality, maternal mortality, and disease death in the population younger than 70 years.

If it is associated with one of the indicators forming HDI, life expectancy at birth will be one of the indicators of the SDGs. Life expectancy at birth will increase if one of the SDGs indicators, namely the neonatal mortality rate, can be suppressed. In its target by 2030, especially for Indonesia aims to reduce neonatal mortality to at least 12 per 1000 births and under-five mortality to as low as 25 per 1000 births. Based on the publication of The Roadmap of SDGs Indonesia, maternal mortality in Indonesia is the highest in Southeast Asia.

In the West Java Province Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMD), it is targeted that in 2023 the stunting prevalence will be 19.2%. Based on the results of the Basic Health Research in 2013 and 2018, respectively and the results of the Under-five Nutrition Status Survey, the prevalence of stunting at the national and provincial levels of West Java, as shown below:

Figure 1: Stunting Prevalence in West Java Province Based on Survey Results

In 2017, a survey called Nutrition Status Monitoring (Pemantauan Status Gizi/PSG) was done by The Ministry of Health's Research and Development Center. The PSG results were used as one of the bases by the National Team for the Acceleration of Poverty Reduction (TNP2K) in determining the priority locus of stunting intervention for 2018. Another aspect that affects the occurrence of stunting is poor environmental health. As one of the factors that affect sanitation and environmental health, there are still many people who defecate openly. An unfavorable environment will increase the risk of environmental-based diseases. This will lead to highly infectious diseases. In analyzing the causes of stunting, the infection status of children under five will affect the absorption of nutrients. If this continues for a long time, it will reduce the body's resistance. Low immunity will result in frequent illness and affect nutritional status (Mistry et al., 2019; Roediger et al., 2020). The high prevalence of stunting significantly affects the achievement of public health degrees. To realize these health development goals, standby

village (Desa Siaga) was developed. Beginning with issuing the Decree of the Minister of Health No. 564/Menkes/SK/VIII/2006 concerning Guidelines for the Implementation and Development of Standby Village.

The process of developing and realizing an active Alert Village did not meet expectations; at that time, the process of community empowerment was Decree of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1529/Menkes/SK/X/2010 concerning General Guidelines for Village Development and Active Standby Villages. The general objective of developing an Active Standby Village is to accelerate the realization of rural and urban communities who care, are responsive, and can recognize, prevent and deal with health problems they face independently so that their health status increases. Standby Village is actively implemented through community empowerment, namely an effort to facilitate the learning process of rural and urban communities in solving problems (Safitri, Nurhadi, Zulkarnain: 2017). To support efforts to develop village community health, its implementation requires an active role from various parties ranging from the central, provincial, district, city, and sub-district governments to villages and sub-districts (Flores et al., 2019; Brar et al., 2020).

Gradually based on the ability of the village to meet the predetermined criteria, the Active Standby Village is sequentially divided into four categories. The categories in stages are as follows: (1) Pratama; (2) Madya; (3) Purnama; and (4) Mandiri (Self-Reliant). A village and sub-district are categorized as Self-Reliant Active Standby Village (Desa Siaga Aktif Mandiri) if they have fulfilled each stage's active standby village's processes and requirements. Based on data processed from Regency and City reports, in general, the achievements of stages in the Active Standby Village category in West Java Province in the last five years are as shown in the image below:

Figure 2: Conditions for Phased the Standby Villages by Strata in West Java Province from 2014 to 2020

Based on a preliminary study through document studies and observations based on report data from the Health Promotion Section, West Java Provincial Health Office, the number of villages is 5,957. Of these, 5,955 have formed Villages in 2019 in a row as follows: primary category as many as 2,285 Villages (36.8%), Middle category as many as 2,516 Villages (42.4%),

Purnama category as many as 748 Villages (12, 6%) and the Self-Reliant category as many as 339 villages (5.7%). Especially for the Garut Regency area, which is the research area, based on preliminary research through document studies that Garut Regency in the implementation of self-reliance, active standby village is still relatively low in achieving self-reliant compared to villages in districts/cities in West Java Province.

Thus, it is necessary to strengthen the aspect of community empowerment so that active standby villages in Garut Regency can achieve health development targets in supporting stunting reduction. Based on the empirical facts above can be a reference to support this research. Furthermore, based on the results of previous research from national and international journals. The search results of national journals conducted by other researchers still concentrate on studies on the implementation of active standby villages (Irwan et al., 2021; Arida et al., 2019; Sugiharto & Kusumandari, 2016), studies related to the active standby village information system (Mulyatno, 2022), evaluation of implementation village health forum (Pradono et al., 2016). The results of international research journals focus on identifying short children aged six years (Purwani & Arvianti, 2020), the risk of stunting in toddlers (McDonough & Davutt, 2011), data analysis on stunting cases (Umanailo et al., 2019), stunting prediction models (Berdinana et al., 2021), and socioeconomic factors of stunting (Mamu et al., 2020; Weng & Peng, 2014; Hidayat & Syahid, 2019). Understanding the research done by previous researchers, the research that has been studied so far has not been carried out by other researchers. Thus, this research has a high level of originality, so research needs to be done.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Community Empowerment

Empowerment is the granting of authority and trust to local communities to determine various forms of development activity programs and their needs through efforts to protect, strengthen, develop, consult and advocate to improve their social welfare level. Empowerment is the granting of authority, a delegation of authority or granting autonomy to lower ranks. The essence of empowerment is an effort to generate all existing capabilities to achieve goals.

Achievement of goals through the growth of motivation, initiative, creativity, and rewards and recognition for those who excel. (Chen et al., 2017) Community empowerment is an effort to increase the capabilities and potential of the community so that people can realize their identity, dignity and worth. It is maximum to survive to develop independently in the social, economic, religious, and cultural fields. Achievement of goals through motivation, initiative, and creative growth, as well as rewards and recognition for those who excel. According to Sulaeman et al. (2017), empowerment can be done using 3 (three) strategies, namely (1) the welfare approach, (2) the development approach, and (3) the empowerment approach.

Meanwhile, Hulme and Turne emphasized that community empowerment is limited by the subject and object dichotomy. The subject and object dichotomy occurs because of power that affects subjects and objects through proximity to the center of power so that the community's

ability, status, ownership, and position will depend heavily on that power. The power possessed by the community will also increase.

Another concept of empowerment theory is the ACTORS theory of empowerment proposed by Djafar et al. (2019), which views society as a subject that can make changes by freeing a person from rigid control and giving the person the freedom to be responsible for ideas, decisions -his decisions and actions. The empowerment intended by Cook and Macaulay is more directed at social and ethical/moral delegation, among others: (a) encouraging fortitude; (b) delegating social authority; (c) managing performance; (d) developing the organization (both local and external); (e) offer cooperation; (f) communicate efficiently; (g) encourage innovation, and (h) resolve the problems that occur.

Using the empowerment concept offered by Cook and Macaulay, the changes that will be produced are planned changes because the inputs to be used in the changes have been anticipated early on so that the outputs that will be produced can be optimally efficient. The study of community empowerment management using the ACTORS framework is as follows: a) authority, groups/communities are given the authority to change their stance or spirit (work ethic) into something that is their own. Thus they feel that the changes made are the product of their desire to change for the better; b) Confidence and competence generate confidence by seeing their ability to be able to change the situation; c) Trust, creating a belief that they have the potential to change and they should be able to (able) to change it; d) Opportunities, providing opportunities for the community to choose what they want so that they can develop themselves according to the potential that exists within the community itself; e) Responsibilities, in making changes must go through management so that it is carried out with full responsibility to change for the better; and f) Support, there needs to support from various parties to make it better. In this case, the expected support apart from the economic, social and cultural side also supports various stakeholders (government, society, and the business world), which is carried out simultaneously without being dominated by one party/factor.

Community Empowerment Goals

In community empowerment, of course, there are goals to be achieved. The purpose of empowerment is to shape individuals and communities to become independent. This independence includes the independence of thinking, acting and controlling what they do. Further, it is necessary to explore what an independent society means. Community independence is a condition experienced by the community which is characterized by the ability to think, decide and do something that is deemed appropriate in order to achieve solving the problems faced by using the resources and abilities consisting of cognitive, conative, psychomotor abilities, with the mobilization of resources owned by the internal environment of the community. Affective condition is a sense owned by the community and expected to be intervened to achieve empowerment in attitudes and behavior. Psychomotor abilities are skills that are owned by the community as an effort to support the community in carrying out development activities. Empowerment in these four aspects (cognitive, conative, affective and psychomotor) will be able to contribute to the creation of the desired community independence

because then, in society, there will be sufficient insight that is equipped with adequate skills, strengthened by a sense of need for development and behavior that is aware of its needs, to achieve community independence a process is needed in the learning process so that the community will acquire a sustainable ability to gain independence (Sulaiman et al., 2019).

In an empowerment process, it is also necessary to pay attention to the collaboration process with various stakeholders, according to (Parantika et al., 2020), stating that in collaboration, there is a model that describes the collaboration process that occurs, then collaboration is also needed in community empowerment. Harsani (2020) said that collaboration would produce a consensus for dialogue and interdependence.

Empowerment Stage

Community empowerment there are stages of empowerment; according to Badruddin et al. (2021), there are three stages in community empowerment, including 1) the stage of forming a caring attitude to increase self-capacity; 2) the stage of changing abilities, skills and knowledge insights have a role in development; 3) increasing intellectual ability to lead to independence. Stages of empowerment, according to Najati et al. (2015), there are four main principles in empowerment (1) Equality, (2) Participation, (3) Independence, and (4) Sustainable. According to Suparji et al. (2018), empowerment is not permanent until the target community can be independent. According to Yuesti & Sumantra (2017) stated that "the learning process in the context of community empowerment will take place gradually (1) The awareness stage and the stage of forming behavior towards conscious and caring behavior so that they feel the need for self-capacity; (2) The ability transformation stage is in the form of knowledge insight, skills to open insight and provide basic skills so that they can take a role in development; (3) The stage of increasing intellectual abilities, skills so that innovative initiatives and abilities are formed to lead to independence.

In addition to paying attention to the spirit of community empowerment, innovation and attention to the culture of the local community or socio-cultural are also needed. Community empowerment, without innovation, will not produce anything new because, according to Azwardi, 2004 that innovation and creativity are found in all aspects of life. Likewise, community culture is the existence of human behavior in society (Yusriani & Alwi, 2018).

Stunting Concept

Stunting is a condition where toddlers have a low height-for-age. This condition is measured by a length and height-for-age more than minus two standard deviations of the WHO child growth standard median. Toddler stunting is a chronic nutritional problem caused by many factors, such as socioeconomic conditions, maternal nutrition during pregnancy, infant morbidity, and lack of nutritional intake in infants. Stunted children will have difficulty achieving optimal physical and cognitive development in the future. Putera et al. (2020) said that stunting is also defined as height according to age below the -2 median standard of the growth curve for children; stunting is a chronic condition of poor linear growth of a child, which is an accumulation of the impact of various factors such as poor nutrition and health before and after the birth of the child.

According to Beal et al. (2018), the fundamental causes of stunting are as follows: (1) Low maternal education; (2) low household income; (3) Unavailability of clean water; (4) Unhealthy environment; (5) Unavailability of food in the nearest market; (6) Food prices are not Affordable; (7) Food safety is not guaranteed; (8) Culture or tradition that is not following a healthy lifestyle; and (9) Lack of strong or inconsistent stakeholder commitment—causing various nutrition and health programs that require support from the non-health sector and other stakeholders to be unable to synergize.

Active Standby Village (Desa Siaga Aktif)

The concept of active standby village is a village whose residents have the readiness of resources and capabilities and the willingness to independently prevent and overcome health problems, disasters, and emergencies. The village referred to here is a kelurahan or other term for a legal community unit with territorial boundaries, which are authorized to regulate and manage interests recognized and respected within the Government of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia.

The standby village's general purpose is to realize a healthy, caring, and responsive village community to health problems in its area. The specific objectives are (a) Increasing the knowledge and awareness of the village community about the importance of health; (b) Increasing awareness and preparedness of village communities against risks and dangers that may cause health problems; (c) Improving environmental health in the village—increased ability and willingness of rural communities to help themselves in the health sector.

Concerning active standby villages, there are several indicators, such as general guidelines for active standby villages and sub-district development based on Minister of Health Regulation No. 1529/Menkes/SK/X/2010, where the Success Indicators of active standby villages are as follows (1) Village Forum Activities (2) The existence of Kader Pembangunan Manusia (Human Development Agent) (3) Ease of public access to essential health services (4) The existence of Upaya Kesehatan Berbasis Masyarakat (Health Efforts by Community Based) (5). There is funding from APBDes (Village Development Budget); (6). There is an active role in the community and mass organizations (7). There are regulations at the village level (8). There is Perilaku Hidup Bersih dan Sehat (Healthy and Clean Lifestyle) development. In its implementation, an active standby village has stages that a village must go through to reach a better stage.

METHOD

The research method used is a combination approach (Mixed-Methods) with a concurrent embedded strategy; in this study, qualitative and quantitative approaches are used together support the research to be undertaken. Research related to empowering active standby village communities in supporting reduction for stunting prevalence in Garut Regency is a series of exploratory activities to study, identify, classify, and understand various phenomena in empowering active standby village communities, so a comprehensive picture is obtained.

Based on the research objectives, the method used is a combination approach (Mixed-Methods). The research strategy used is concurrent embedded. Qualitative methods involve interpretive and naturalistic approaches, so qualitative researchers must study various things in the natural environment related to various aspects of the study being explored in this case concerning the model of community empowerment in active standby villages.

In the quantitative method for collecting data, what needs to be explained is related to the population and sample. The population in this study were villages in Garut Regency, which consisted of 442 villages. In calculating the sample in this study, it was carried out in 2 stages, namely determining the sample of villages that were included in the category of Pratama, Madya, Purnama & Mandiri villages, and determining the sample of village representatives based on the village category in Garut Regency. The determination of village samples based on categorization in the categories of Pratama, Madya, Purnama and Mandiri villages was carried out based on random cluster sampling; in this case, there were four categories. Meanwhile, the determination of the village sample was based on purposive sampling, namely the technique of selecting samples based on objectives where the desired fundamental objective in selecting this sample is to know the region's characteristics from the current regional background, which is different (heterogeneous).

Based on the research problem, the strategy suitable for research is to use analysis in the soft system methodology (SSM) approach. The soft system methodology (SSM) method is also action research aiming to solve complex problems. Achieving a Self-Reliant Active Standby Village is a complex activity involving the organization's various parties, both internal and external. The use of a Soft System Methodology (SSM) approach to solve the problem in this research is to build a model of empowering the village community to be active and self-reliant to reduce stunting in the Garut Regency.

Data collection techniques in qualitative methods were carried out to obtain primary and secondary data. Primary data were obtained from interviews, FGDs and observations in Garut Regency. Meanwhile, secondary data is obtained from reviewing essential documents related to implementing self-reliant active standby village related to stunting reduction. In this study, to conduct an analysis is to carry out a study process to identify the structure of a phenomenon; the analysis is carried out by examining the phenomenon as a whole, as well as the parts that make up the phenomenon and the relationship between the elements forming a phenomenon. The purpose of using SSM in this study is to build a model of community empowerment in active standby villages to reduce stunting in Garut Regency. To meet the objectives of this study, the SSM analysis consists of (1) CATWOE analysis, (2) Role analysis and (3) Social System Analysis.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Quantitative data was carried out through a questionnaire method to representatives from 421 villages and 21 kelurahan; based on the questionnaire results, there were 616 respondents consisting of representatives of the village community, as many as 52 villages. Based on the

data obtained, as many as 616 respondents consisting of the male sex 20.6 percent and female as much as 79.4 percent, where women dominate respondents

Figure 3: Number of respondents to the questionnaire by gender

The respondent's data regarding age levels ranged from 18 years to over 62 years. Where the age category in this respondent is dominated by ages 29 to 39 years, as much as 39.4 percent, while the 40 - 50 years age group is 35.7 percent, for the age group 18 to 28 years, it is 11.2 percent while age group 51 to 61 years by 13.1 percent.

Figure 4: Number of respondents to the questionnaire by age

Based on the respondent's data regarding the last position when filling out the questionnaire, it consisted of structural and functional positions. Structural answers range from echelon 4 to echelon 3, while functional positions consist of general and specific functions. Based on the respondent's data, it is dominated by general functional.

Figure 5: Number of respondents to the questionnaire by position

Based on the education level, the respondents consisted of Senior High schools with the highest education, S3. Based on available data, the high school education group had the highest number at 53.7 percent. In comparison, the undergraduate education group had 30.4 percent of respondents, then the D3 and S2 education groups spread out from 616 respondents from all villages in the Garut Regency.

Figure 6: Number of respondents to the questionnaire based on the last education

Based on the results of the questionnaire survey distributed at the research locus on the implementation of the Active Standby Village in supporting the reduction of stunting prevalence with the ACTORS concept, the following data were generated:

Table 1: Questionnaire results from respondents

No	Statement	Rating Percentage			
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Authority	51	38	6	4
2	Confidence and competence	43	42	11	4
3	Trust	42	43	16	4
4	Opportunities	47	42	8	4
5	Responsibilities	45	43	8	4
6	Support (dukungan)	47	41	8	5

Source: data proceed

Based on the analysis results, the results show that the variable authority having an assessment score of 51 percent, provides the highest rating compared to other variables; aspects of authority, opportunity, responsibility and support need to be maintained and strengthened in active standby village management. For other variables, it is necessary to increase the aspect of self-confidence and commitment as well as the confidence possessed by active standby village administrators in the Garut Regency.

In building a model for empowering the active standby village community in supporting the reduction in the prevalence of stunting in the Garut Regency, it is based on the implementation of the current Self-reliant Active Standby Village community empowerment in the Garut Regency. The current condition does not yet have a pattern for empowering the active standby village community. The researcher used the soft system methodology (SSM) to build this model. The purpose of using SSM in this study was to build a model for empowering rural communities to be active and independent in supporting the reduction of stunting prevalence in the Garut Regency. To meet the objectives of this study, the SSM analysis consists of (1) CATWOE analysis, and (2) Role analysis. The description of building the model is as follows:

The Problem Situation is Unstructured, which reveals that the Problem under Study is Problematic.

In discussing the steps in the SSM analysis, it is to reveal the problems studied, namely regarding the empowerment of the Self-Reliant Active Standby Village in supporting the reduction of stunting prevalence in Garut Regency. As previously described, there are problems in learning where the level of achievement cannot be carried out optimally; problems influence this in community empowerment, including problems of community participation and clean and healthy lifestyles that have not been maximized. As for the problems in community empowerment, it was found that the fundamental problems in the active standby village were: a) the low participation of the community in the implementation of the active standby village; b) The subordinate role of stakeholders, including community organizations participating in active standby villages; c) The lack of public understanding about health results in the development of a clean and healthy lifestyle that is still not well understood; d) Lack of innovation in supporting funding sources from government funds so that to achieve budget independence is still not optimal; e) Human development cadres already exist in quantity but in terms of quality need to be strengthened in understanding their duties and functions; and f) Human resources that need to be improved to clearly understand the objectives of an independent, active social village.

Knowing this problematic situation is hoped that it can be a meeting point for formulating future learning so that it can be better and increase the active standby village to become self-reliant. Furthermore, an analysis related to existing problems is carried out with CATWOE analysis, role analysis and system analysis, which are described as follows:

CATWOE Analysis

The explanation of the CATWOE analysis is as follows:

Table 2: Analysis CATWOE

No.	CATWOE Components	Result Definition
1	Customer	The village community in Garut Regency
2	Actor	Village Government
3	Transformation	The process of community empowerment in supporting Self-Reliant Active Standby Village needs to be intervened through community empowerment models that can support it
4	Worldview	The community empowerment model needs to be formulated to solve problems related to the achievements of the Self-Reliant Active Standby Village
No.	CATWOE Components	Result Definition
5	Owner	Public Health Office
6	Environmental constraints	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Limited capacity and capability of cadres as administrators in managing active standby villages 2. The community's low understanding of the active standby village concept and implementation 3. There is no solid collaboration for support of Self-reliant Active Standby Village, so there is still no budget support from other sources 4. The understanding of public health in a clean and healthy lifestyle is not yet maximal. 5. Human Resource that needs to be improved

Source: data proceed

Through this CATWOE analysis, it can be seen that in the aspect of collaboration and innovation, collaboration and innovation play an essential role in changing the community empowerment process in the future. For this reason, the development of the model to be built must pay attention to the CATWOE analysis as a basis for preparing the model for empowering the village community to be active and independent in Garut Regency.

Role Analysis

The role analysis is carried out to identify the party who is the problem owner or problem owner with authority to intervene in the model empowering the Self-reliant Active Standby Village community in Garut Regency. Based on the interview results, the Sindanggalih Village Secretary stated that the Village Government has a strategic role in implementing an active standby village by involving various elements of the village apparatus community. Based on this, the empowerment model for the village community is active and independent in Garut Regency in carrying out its authority in village government activities and coordinating with sub-districts, DPMD and other supporting agencies in Garut Regency.

Regarding the problem solver, the village government and other elements have the authority to intervene in the empowerment of the active standby village community in the Garut Regency in the form of activities and coordination with relevant stakeholders such as health cadres, KPM, and elements of local government. Thus, the strategic role of the village government in Garut Regency in carrying out the empowerment of the active standby village community has the authority to coordinate and ensure that all criteria in the active standby village can be implemented thoroughly and can increase at the active standby village stage which was initially Pratama, Madya, Purnama and Mandiri in the end all of them bear the Self-reliant Active Standby Villages.

Based on the results of this role analysis based on facts in the field based on field observations and documentation studies that the village government has a strategic role in supporting the achievement of empowerment of the Self-reliant Active Standby Village community supported by other stakeholders so that the village government has an essential role as problem owner and problem solver in empowering the village community on Self-reliant Active Standby Village in Garut Regency.

Social Systems Analysis

The analysis of this social system aims to determine one's social position in empowering the village community to be active and independent in Garut Regency so that later interventions on the system under study are culturally acceptable. In this case, a person's position relates to institutional positions such as the Village Head, Camat, Head of Service and other related elements. Based on the results of interviews and semi-FGDs attended by active standby village administrators in Karangpawitan District, which was attended by around 45 community representatives in Garut Regency, it was found that related to the institutional position is associated with aspects of the social system according to Health Cadres from Karangpawitan Sub District in Garut Regency, explaining that The Village and District Governments have an essential role in the implementation of the empowerment of the independent, Self-reliant Active Standby community in Garut Regency because they are always in direct contact with various activities with the community. This was also obtained by the head of the public health section of the Garut Regency Health Office, who said that concerning parties who can intervene culturally, it can be carried out by the village government, sub-district and village community empowerment services, Health Office as a party that always coordinates various activities in the community.

Based on the description above, it is true that the implementation of local government and village governments has carried out their duties according to their respective fields but cannot be separated from the culture or customs in each village. Based on field observations, it shows that the culture in Garut Regency tends to have similarities in terms of character or culture in each village in the Garut Regency. Thus, the pattern of earnest work and perseverance work becomes a habit in everyday life at work. So that community empowerment activities in the active standby village in Garut Regency can be carried out inseparable from the culture or customs that exist in each of these villages. Thus, socio-culture plays an essential role in the success of the active standby village program to achieve self-reliance.

The Situational Problem Expressed is the Preparation of a Rich Picture to Reveal the Structure of the Problem in Empowering the Active Standby Village Community

The second stage in formulating this model is by compiling a rich picture that provides an overview of the implementation of community empowerment in the active standby village in Garut Regency. An accurate picture related to implementing an active-standby village to become independent requires stages that can achieve the stage indicators in the active standby village. The current model being implemented has problems that must be resolved so that the community empowerment activities in the active standby village community become better independent. A detailed explanation can be seen in the following table:

Table 3: Correlation of criteria for active standby villages with elements of the concept of community empowerment

No	Active Alert Village Criteria	Elements of Community Empowerment
1.	Village/Urban Forum	1. Authority 2. Confidence and Ability 3. Confidence 4. Opportunity 5. Responsibility 6. Support
2.	Community Empowerment Cadres	
3.	Easy Access to Basic Health Services	
4.	Posyandu and UKBM	
5.	Funding support for health activities in the Village	
6.	Community Participation and Community Organizations	
7.	Village Head/Regent/Mayor Regulation	
8.	Guidance of Clean and Healthy Lifestyle in the Household	

The root definition, in this case, is "Activity village community empowerment activities are a system that must be carried out following predetermined provisions, but during the implementation process, there are dynamics, namely the achievements of the Pratama, middle, complete, and independent village stages are not appropriate. With what is planned, it is necessary to intervene to solve the existing problems through the model of empowering the active standby village community in the Garut Regency. "

Understanding the root definition above is used to limit the objectives. The researcher focuses on building effective empowerment of active standby village communities in Garut Regency to become a Self-reliant Active Standby Village. The formulation of the model at this stage is to build a conceptual model based on actual conditions in the field at this time by paying attention to various problems that exist in the field in the implementation of empowering the village community on active and independent standby in Garut Regency. In addition to paying attention to natural conditions in the field, he also pays attention to the development of knowledge and technology, which is currently proliferating in various activities, including those used in various activities in the process of empowering villages on active standby independently. The empowerment of the village community on active and independent standby in Garut Regency, which is proposed is as follows:

Figure 7: Conceptual Model of Community Empowerment the Self-Reliant Active Standby Village

Based on the description above, community empowerment is a process in which the active standby village is a mandate from the institution following the Decree of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia No. 1529/Menkes/SK/X/2010 concerning general guidelines for the development of active standby villages and sub-districts. Based on this mandate, implementation is carried out by each region which is monitored by the health office in each Regency/City.

The village government must implement eight criteria to achieve a Self-Reliant Active Standby Village. Each criterion assesses the active standby village category, which is Pratama, Madya, Purnama and Mandiri. Achieving these stages requires an assessment that meets the standards of each of these stages. To achieve this, a community empowerment process is needed to support the achievement of the Self-Reliant Active Standby Village.

The concept of the ACTORS theory of empowerment proposed by Fenn (2012) in its implementation follows the facts in the field. However, due to current developments, other elements have been found based on field observations, namely the elements of collaboration and innovation, because in ACTORS theory, these aspects have not been accommodated and based on the results of the study developed the ACTORS theory with two other aspects, namely collaboration and innovation which are very important in community empowerment in current conditions. The process of community empowerment is also influenced by other aspects, namely socio-cultural, namely community culture, where the management of this Self-Reliant Active Standby Village is within the scope of the village, which cannot be separated from the cultural aspects of the local community as local content that can support the process of achieving community empowerment to achieve an active standby village independent.

Comparison of 4 with 2 is to Compare Step 4 to the Results of Step 2 to Test the Model and Identify Aspects that can be improved on the Conceptual Model.

At this stage, the researcher compares the model with the existing conditions in managing the active standby village in the Garut district. In the existing condition model that has been carried out so far it has not been structured because no community empowerment model is a reference in its implementation; after research has been carried out in its implementation, some problems must be resolved, and it is necessary to develop an active standby village community empowerment model in Garut Regency. The comparison is as follows:

Table 4: Comparison of the existing model and the research model

Existing Condition	The Self-Reliant Active Standby Village Community Empowerment Model
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Institutional mandate 2. Village community forum on active alert 3. Implementation of the eight criteria for the standby village to reach the Pratama, Madya, Purnama and Mandiri stages 4. Community participation in supporting the program. 5. Pratama active standby villages as many as 217 villages, intermediate as many as 194 villages, the Purnama as many as 30 villages and Mandiri as many as one village 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Self-Reliant active standby village community empowerment model uses the ACTORS theory approach and the findings of researchers in the field 2. The community empowerment process uses eight aspects of empowerment 3. Involvement of community and stakeholder participation through 8 criteria for Active Standby Village 4. Monitoring and evaluating the achievement of the Active Standby Village target 5. The socio-cultural-based approach to implementing Active Standby Village empowerment

Feasible, Desirable Changes, Namely the Identification and Intervention of Models that Want and Deserve to be Changed or Desired

At this stage, researchers identify and intervene in models that can be changed from the model made in step 4. Based on the results of the model that has been made, several aspects need to be improved so that the model is better. To refine the model that has been built, a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) was held which was held on July 19, 2022, at the Garut Regency BAPPEDA Office. The FGD was led by the Secretary of BAPPEDA and attended by representatives from the Regional Apparatus, representatives of Professional Organizations and Community Organizations related to village community empowerment and stunting handling in Garut Regency. Based on the results of the FGD, several inputs were obtained, namely, according to the Head of the Public Health Division of the Garut Regency Health Office: "I strongly agree that the empowerment of self-reliance, Active Standby Village communities is used as an approach to reducing stunting. During the verification of Active Standby Villages, the criteria that are relatively difficult to achieve are the eighth criteria, namely Clean and Healthy Life Behavior (PHBS), because there are ten indicators with a target of 80% each, all of which must be achieved. If one of the indicators is not achieved, it cannot be categorized as a Self-Reliant Active Standby Village. The indicator is that no one smokes in the house. The Village Indicator has provided an adequate budget for the health sector. Collaboration of all related sectors with

all elements of society and other elements is needed to achieve the target indicator. Stunting intervention can be through activating active standby villages through the formation of other UKBMs and entering prevention in youth groups through Karang Taruna."

Meanwhile, according to the Secretary of the Garut District Health Office that: "The word collaboration, innovation and socio-cultural becomes an important aspect in community empowerment, it is hoped that these three aspects can be implemented properly. The Head of Regional Planning and Development Agency (BAPPEDA) stated that: "Active Alert Villages are needed to support the acceleration of stunting reduction in Garut Regency, which currently has a prevalence of 35% (based on the Status Survey. To support this, planning needs to be done, synergizing so that Active Standby Village is one of the diplomatic intervention efforts in stunting handling." Furthermore, the identification that can be done as an intervention effort is as follows: 1) Ensuring that the empowerment process carried out supports all achievements against the eight criteria set by the government; 2) There is a need for monitoring and evaluation aspects during the process of achieving criteria so that there is an increase in stages in active standby villages, and 3) There needs to be an explanation that the whole community can understand on each of the eight criteria in order to have the same understanding regarding the aims and objectives to be implemented.

Through the results of the input from the built model regarding the identification and interventions that can be done to complete the empowerment model for the village community on self-reliant, active and standby in Garut Regency.

Action to Improve the Problem Situation is a Real Action Taken to Improve the Model in the Real World

The last stage is to take real action in the form of model changes that have been made if there are essential things that need to be done as a concrete form for model improvement. Improvements to the existing model as in stage 4 and following the results of identification in stage 6, the model is refined as a form of real improvement so that it can be adequately implemented in the field. The form of change as a refinement of the empowerment model for the village community on active, self-reliant and standby in Garut Regency can be seen in the image below:

Figure 8: The Final Model of Community Empowerment in the Self-Reliant Active Standby Village

Based on the picture of the active standby village community empowerment model above, the refinement of the model is a tangible manifestation of the results of this study. Thus, the model can be accurately implemented in all active standby villages in Garut Regency and other areas to guide achieving self-reliance in Active Standby Village.

The monitoring and evaluation process is carried out to ensure eight criteria in achieving the stages in the Self-Reliant Active Standby Village. The phasing process in the active standby village has four stages, and each stage has achievements that must be completed. In order to anticipate that achievement can be made, good monitoring and evaluation are needed to ensure that they can be achieved according to the plans each village government has scheduled.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research at this conclusion, the following description is presented: 1) The implementation of empowering the active standby village community in Garut Regency based on ACTORS theory provides an understanding that there are aspects of authority, opportunity, responsibility and support quantitatively and qualitatively showing the results of the implementation have been going well, for aspects of self-confidence & ability and confidence provide good understanding but need to be strengthened on these aspects based on quantitative and qualitative results; 2) The results of research related to community empowerment in the form of a model of empowering the village community in active standby

independently are the result of the integration of conceptual thinking and the results of reality that complement each other in producing the model, and as a solution in achieving Self-reliance, Active Standby Village in Garut Regency.

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